

High school students' experiences with social skills in an educational institution

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Abstract— The objective The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) to which the inquiry made its contributions was Goal 4, which promoted equitable, quality and inclusive education, and specifically with target 4.7, which referred to Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and Education for Global Citizenship (EfGC), being a fundamental approach to promote a peaceful and tolerant society. The objective of this research was to analyze the experiences of secondary school students on social skills in an educational institution in Lima, in the year 2024. Methodologically, the study had a qualitative approach, of basic type and phenomenological design. The key participants were 11. An interview guide was used as a tool for data collection, which were validated through expert judgment. Concluding, regarding the social skills of students in an educational institution, Lima-2024 revealed that they may have emotional difficulties, limitations in asking personal or general questions, and difficulty analyzing and reflecting before making decisions. Furthermore, they prefer positive feelings and find it important to clarify accusations, and they require mental organization or personal planning for a successful coexistence.

Key words: Social skills, social competences, school, peaceful coexistence, decision making.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, growing attention has been given to the role of social skills in fostering comprehensive education and personal development. Social skills are essential for the holistic growth of students in basic education, as they enhance emotional regulation, self-esteem, assertiveness, and the ability to act autonomously and responsibly. Programs designed to strengthen these skills have been shown to reduce aggressive behaviors and promote positive attitudes across educational, family, and social contexts. Moreover, they enable students to acquire cognitive, socio-emotional, and interpersonal competencies that are crucial for both academic success and personal well-being. However, in today's context of increasing insecurity and violence, such issues have a direct impact on the school environment, often leading to conflicts that must be addressed proactively. Since schools serve as vital spaces for learning and social interaction, it is essential to reinforce socio-emotional abilities and conflict-resolution strategies to foster healthier coexistence. This perspective aligns with the global challenges identified by UNESCO, which emphasizes the importance of integrating social skills development within educational systems to promote more inclusive, equitable, and supportive learning environments. (Nguyen et al., 2022).

The United Nations Children's Fund identified several key challenges in the development of essential skills, including low learning outcomes in fundamental areas such as literacy and numeracy, a lack of emphasis on socio-emotional competencies, limited digital literacy across all stages of life, and few opportunities to acquire job-specific skills that align with labor market demands. (UNICEF, 2020)

Consequently, many students in Latin America and the Caribbean have not developed the necessary competencies to succeed in education, the workforce, or active social participation. This issue is closely related to Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which advocates for equitable, quality, and inclusive education—particularly Target 4.7, which focuses on Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), a Culture of Peace, and Global Citizenship Education (GCED). Additionally, Target 4.a has promoted the creation and adaptation of inclusive and safe educational facilities that respond to the needs of all learners, including persons with disabilities, while fostering tolerance and contributing to the development of peaceful and non-violent societies. This approach is considered essential for promoting mutual understanding and building more cohesive, peaceful communities (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean [ECLAC], 2019).

In Spanish-speaking countries, approximately 80% of children and adolescents have experienced physical and/or psychological aggression within their family or school environments. Moreover, 45% of Peruvian adolescents have been victims of some form of sexual violence, including physical contact (National Institute of Statistics and Informatics [INEI], 2016). Similarly, a joint study conducted by the Ministry of Women and Vulnerable Populations and UNICEF revealed that 82.9% of adolescents reported experiencing physical or emotional aggression at school. Psychological aggression was found to occur more frequently than physical aggression, with higher rates than those reported within family settings. Among female students, 80.6% experienced psychological aggression and 44.8% experienced physical aggression. Among male students, 79.0% reported psychological aggression and 53.2% reported physical aggression, most often perpetrated by their peers at school (Ministry of Women and Vulnerable Populations & UNICEF, 2016a).

To address this purpose, the following research questions were formulated. The general research question was: What are the experiences related to social skills among secondary school students in an educational institution in Lima, 2024? The specific research questions were: What are the experiences of secondary school students regarding basic social skills, advanced social skills, emotion-related skills, alternatives to aggression, stress-coping skills, and planning skills within an educational institution in Lima, 2024?

At the international level, Etikawati et al. (2023) conducted a qualitative study in Indonesia aimed at exploring the communication skills of school-age children. Data were collected through interviews in which students shared their perspectives and experiences. The research was carried out in three phases: the first involved nine children aged 10 to 12; the second included 24 fifth-grade students; and the third employed the focus group discussion (FGD) technique with 15 parents whose children were in grades four to six. The data were analyzed using an inductive thematic approach, which led to the identification of eight key themes: receptive skills, linguistic accuracy, contextual understanding, openness, assertiveness, self-confidence, social sensitivity, and politeness. The study reached two main conclusions. First, receptive communication skills also encompassed the understanding of nonverbal messages; and second, the structure of these skills included components related to social competence. This competence was linked to both individualistic and collectivist cultural traits found in Indonesian families, reflecting a balance between maintaining social harmony and fostering autonomy. The findings provided a valuable foundation for developing assessment tools and educational programs aimed at strengthening communicative competence among school-age students.

At the international level, Ansari (2024) conducted a mixed-methods study in Pakistan that examined the development of non-cognitive abilities—such as social skills and life competencies—among students. Using a sequential design that combined quantitative and qualitative approaches, the research involved a sample of 263 students, along with 16 additional students, 8 teachers, and 4 school administrators. The findings revealed that while students demonstrated social skills and basic life competencies, schools did not prioritize

the development of these abilities, thereby limiting students' holistic growth. The study also highlighted that the school system and institutional structures exert a significant influence on the development of such skills.

In Norway, Vestad and Tharaldsen (2022) conducted a qualitative study on social and emotional competencies, focusing on students' experiences. The study aimed to promote five key social and emotional skills (SEL): attention, relationships, regulation, growth mindset, and conflict resolution. Data were collected through focus group interviews with early secondary school students, resulting in a final sample of 26 participants. The findings revealed that students perceived mindfulness, problem-solving, and a growth mindset as valuable strategies for managing academic stress, whereas emotional regulation and interpersonal skills were reported as the most challenging to apply in practice.

In Indonesia, Salimi et al. (2020) conducted a qualitative case study aimed at analyzing the learning processes that influence the development of students' social competencies. The sample included students, teachers, and school principals selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, observations, and document analysis. The findings indicated that learning should be implemented through diverse methods, models, and media, involving parents and offering a variety of activities that foster interpersonal skills. The study concluded that school-based learning plays a positive role in strengthening students' interpersonal competencies.

Another study by Irmansyah et al. (2020) in Indonesia aimed to enhance children's social interaction skills through the use of modified traditional games, such as *Gobak Sodor*. Employing a qualitative approach, the researchers used observation techniques and unstructured interviews with two physical education teachers and sixteen students. Observation and interview guides were utilized as data collection instruments. The findings indicated that the modified game promoted key abilities such as personal responsibility, teamwork, communication, and mutual care. The study concluded that the development of social competencies requires time and a continuous learning process, suggesting that adapting traditional games can serve as an effective educational strategy.

In Ecuador, Paredes and Ramos (2020) examined cooperative learning as an effective educational tool, aiming to assess its current implementation and its relationship with collective engagement. The study employed a mixed-methods approach with an explanatory design, combining questionnaires, interviews, and observation guides. The results indicated that cooperative learning is less frequently applied in some subject areas but more common in others. The researchers concluded that teachers generally agree that this approach fosters teamwork and develops social skills through relevant activities and guided instruction. The sample consisted of four teachers and sixty-nine students from three levels of upper secondary education. Data were collected using the *Classroom Cooperative Learning Questionnaire* (CACCL) and an observation guide assessing aspects such as group organization, clarity of rules, interpersonal relationships, and the teacher's role.

The theory of social and family factors have a significant impact on education, producing both positive and negative effects. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines adolescence (ages 12–17) as a stage marked by physical, emotional, and social transformations that shape behavior and personality, often influenced by actions accepted or rejected by society (Saavedra Meléndez et al., 2021). This developmental phase, characterized by biological changes and the influence of inadequate family models, can contribute to various behavioral and emotional difficulties. However, brain maturation during adolescence allows for gradual improvement in emotional and behavioral regulation—though it requires time, guidance, and effort to cultivate social skills and awareness of one's own behavior. Among the main factors influencing the development of these abilities are the lack of emotional support and the presence of family conflict, educational systems that fail to emphasize emotional management and interpersonal competence, the absence of role models demonstrating adequate socio-emotional skills, and psychological challenges such as anxiety or depression that hinder emotional understanding and social interaction. Additionally, the lack of institutional policies that promote social skill development among teachers—and the insufficient training

to create safe and supportive learning environments—can negatively affect students' motivation and engagement in the learning process (Zela Bravo, 2022).

From the perspective of Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence, the focus lies on the ability to identify, understand, and manage one's own emotions as well as those of others. Goleman argues that emotional intelligence is as significant as, or perhaps even more influential than, intellectual quotient (IQ) in achieving success in both personal and professional spheres. The theory encompasses five key components: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills (Goleman, 1995). Regarding self-awareness, it refers to the capacity to recognize and understand one's internal emotions, strengths, and weaknesses. It involves being attuned to one's feelings and how they influence decisions and actions. Meanwhile, self-regulation is the ability to monitor and appropriately guide emotional responses rather than reacting impulsively. It includes traits such as self-control, adaptability, reliability, and innovation. This ability enables individuals to maintain emotional balance in challenging situations and sustain a positive outlook when facing difficulties (Goleman, 1995).

According to the Specialized System for Reporting School Violence Cases (SiseVe), 83.5% of documented school aggression incidents occurred in public institutions, and 54.2% of the affected students were from the secondary level, having been assaulted primarily by their peers during their school years (Ministry of Education of Peru [MINEDU], 2019). In response to the rise in such incidents after the return to in-person classes, MINEDU took action to address these patterns of school violence. In 2022, 12,099 cases of aggression were reported in the SiseVe system—an alarming increase compared to the 768 cases reported in 2021 (MINEDU, 2022). This information revealed a lack of strong social skills among students, which hindered their ability to develop essential competencies for overcoming challenges and achieving a constructive transition into adulthood. Therefore, fostering the development of social skills among students became crucial, with a particular emphasis on the important role of adults in modeling such behaviors.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. *Design*

The design of this study employed a hermeneutic-phenomenological research design, which allows for the examination and interpretation of students' lived experiences from their own perspective. This approach aims to explore the essence of those experiences, interpreting them faithfully and without distortion, while preserving the integrity of the data and avoiding premature conclusions about their impact on school coexistence. In this sense, phenomenology seeks to understand the deeper meaning of participants' subjective experiences, acknowledging them as a legitimate and valuable source of knowledge (Castillo, 2021).

2.2. *Participants*

The population was defined as a group of individuals sharing common characteristics. According to Hernández and Mendoza (2018), the population refers to the set of elements with shared attributes that represent the entirety of what is being studied and are deliberately selected by the researcher. In this study, the population consisted of secondary school students registered in the Tutoring and Coexistence area due to issues related to behavior, violence, or family problems affecting their academic development, totaling 30 students in 2024. The sampling method was non-probabilistic and based on convenience. Since the research design was phenomenological, the study worked with key participants, comprising eleven (11) students (Hernández & Mendoza, 2018).

2.3. *Measuring instruments*

For this research pure research was the approach, also known as basic research, was chosen in accordance with the OECD/Eurostat Oslo Manual (2018). Its main purpose was to gather and analyze relevant information regarding the experiences of secondary school students in relation to social skills within an educational institution. As noted by Arias & Covinos (2021), this type of research does not aim to solve problems directly but rather to provide theoretical and methodological support for other studies. Its significance lies in its ability to explore arguments through a rigorous, representative, and systematic investigative approach, contributing to the advancement of knowledge by collecting data on the specific characteristics of the phenomenon under study.

2.4. *Procedure*

The procedure for data analysis involved conducting the interviews and subsequently transcribing them. The inductive method was applied to the data, as the research began with specific ideas that moved from the parts to the whole, and through data analysis, general conclusions were derived from the triangulated information. The process included the following steps: (1) creation of a categorization matrix, (2) coding, (3) categorization, (4) triangulation, and finally, the construction of abstract knowledge (Cisterna, 2005). Triangulation was carried out by comparing participants' opinions, which allowed for the generation of new categories leading to the final conclusions (Creswell, 2014).

III. RESULTS

Regarding the results of the general objective was to understand the lived experiences of secondary school students regarding social skills in an educational institution, an analysis of the collected data was presented. The discussion addressed the specific objectives related to the category of social skills, describing the experiences associated with planning abilities and recognizing their impact on the development of autonomy and personal organization for achieving learning goals.

The report included 11 students from the 6th and 7th cycles of secondary education. The main category of social skills and its subcategories were organized using Atlas.ti V.23 software, which enabled the identification of connections and patterns within the analyzed topic. The process included the creation of co-occurrence tables to observe relationships between codes, complemented by data triangulation to ensure a thorough analysis of the students' experiences related to the category of social skills.

TABLE I
CODES WITH CONCURRENCES

Código	Coocurrencia
Mirar a la persona	9
Escuchar atentamente	9
Hacer preguntas personales o generales	10
Buscar temas en común o afinidades	7
Hacer que la conversación fluya o se alargue	7
Sentimiento de bienestar o alegría	9
Reconocimiento de la acción positiva realizada	7

Percepción positiva/emocional del otro	8
Malestar emocional	11
Apoyo mutuo y acompañamiento	7
Conciencia emocional y autorregulación	7
Reflexión, responsabilización y reparación del conflicto	7
Aclaración directa de la acusación	8
Análisis y reflexión personal antes de decidir	10
Priorización por dificultad	7
Organización mental o planificación personal	8

Note: From ATLAS.Ti.

For the qualitative analysis of data regarding the students' lived experiences related to their social skills, ATLAS.ti software was employed, allowing the identification of co-occurrence patterns among codes. Although a balanced integration of the established subcategories was anticipated, the results revealed certain inconsistencies in how the students interact with their peers, suggesting notable weaknesses in the development of key social skills.

Fig. 1 Unit of categories

Fig. 1 presents First, the study described the experiences related to basic social skills, identifying how students communicated in their interpersonal interactions and applied norms of courtesy across different

contexts. Second, advanced social skills were explored, analyzing how students demonstrated leadership, cooperated with peers, and participated in conflict resolution. Third, the analysis focused on skills associated with emotion management, particularly regarding emotional regulation and the practice of empathy in school situations. Fourth, alternative skills to aggression were examined to understand how students related to others, whether they practiced self-control, and how they resolved conflicts—allowing for an interpretation of their ability to handle challenging situations and how these dynamics influenced school coexistence. Fifth, the study analyzed how students coped with stressful situations, identifying their emotional reactions, conflicts, and complaints, as well as how they managed external pressure and environmental influences. Finally, experiences related to planning skills were described, recognizing their impact on the development of autonomy and personal organization in achieving learning goals.

Fig. 1 Emerging

The subcategories derived from the main unit of analysis—or central category—social skills, were organized in accordance with the theoretical framework proposed by Goldstein et al. (1989). This framework integrates the contributions of Bandura, Vygotsky, and Goleman to establish six progressive levels of social skills: basic skills, advanced skills, skills related to emotions, alternative skills to aggression, stress management skills, and planning skills. This model reflects a gradual progression in the reflective analysis of students' abilities, aligning with the main objective of this study—to understand the lived experiences of secondary school students regarding their social skills in an educational institution in Lima, 2024. Based on this framework, each subcategory and its corresponding emergent codes were analyzed, identified through the examination of interviews conducted with eleven students from the sixth and seventh educational cycles. This analytical process enabled the study to address its specific objectives and fulfill its overall research purpose.

Fig. 2 Emerging

Figure 3 indicates regarding the first indicator, there was a clear tendency toward active listening and maintaining eye contact—behaviors perceived by the participants as expressions of respect and genuine attentiveness. This receptive dimension proved to be the most developed, showing high recurrence across the corresponding codes. One participant stated, “I look straight into her eyes; I listen with my eyes” (STUDENT5), illustrating how these behaviors were naturally integrated, though not always complemented by equally strong expressive skills.

Fig. 4 Emerging

Figure 4 shows this subcategory revealed that skills related to emotional awareness were in the process of consolidation. The students not only recognized their emotions but also engaged in strategies for self-

regulation and empathy-building. Nonetheless, certain challenges persisted—particularly in open emotional expression and conflict management—which could lead to internal tension or isolation if not adequately addressed. These findings reaffirmed the need to promote sustained educational spaces where adolescents can name, feel, and share their experiences without fear of judgment. As Goldstein (1989) asserts, the healthy management of emotions is a fundamental component of social competence and a vital foundation for coexistence and personal well-being.

Fig. 5 Emerging codes from the subcategory development of an action plan

Figure 5 shows findings that indicates that the students possessed various resources to prevent aggressive behaviors and manage their emotions constructively, both in their interpersonal relationships and in their inner world. Notably, the intentional use of learned strategies stood out, suggesting a positive impact from previous interventions in socio-emotional education. However, certain areas were identified as needing further development. Although most students avoided direct confrontation, they did not always manage to verbally express their feelings or resolve conflicts assertively. In many cases, emotional control manifested through withdrawal or silent restraint, which could lead to emotional exhaustion if not supported by spaces for expression and emotional validation.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained show The social skills of students at an educational institution in Lima-2024 revealed that they experience emotional difficulties, have limitations in asking personal or general questions, and struggle to analyze and reflect before making decisions. Furthermore, they value positive emotions and consider it important to clarify misunderstandings or accusations. They also require mental organization and personal planning to achieve healthy coexistence. These challenges hinder their ability to interact effectively with their peers, affecting their current social relationships and potentially influencing their future peer interactions.

The results were supported by previous studies, such as Etikawati et al. (2023), who found that students exhibited difficulties in receptive skills, linguistic accuracy, contextual understanding, openness, assertiveness, self-confidence, social sensitivity, and politeness. Receptive communication skills also involved the interpretation of nonverbal messages, and the structure of these skills was found to include elements related to social competence. The latter was associated with both individualistic and collectivist cultural traits, combining an emphasis on social harmony with the promotion of autonomy. The findings of that study provided a valuable foundation for developing assessment tools or educational programs aimed at strengthening communicative competence among school-aged students.

The results were supported by the theories of Bandura et al. (1961), who developed the Social Learning Theory, which explains how individuals acquire behaviors, skills, and attitudes through observation, imitation, and interaction with others. This model posits that the consequences of behavior (reinforcements or punishments) influence whether the learner decides to replicate it. Motivation is also linked to self-efficacy, referring to an individual's confidence in their ability to successfully perform a specific task. Upon analyzing the different theories, Goldstein's Social Competence Theory emerged as the most suitable framework, as its classification system allows for a detailed and practical understanding of the various dimensions of social skills. Its structured approach enables both the identification of deficiencies and the implementation of effective strategies to enhance social skills across different populations.

In this sense, the category of social skills encompasses the ability to establish effective interactions with others. It includes abilities such as active listening, conflict resolution, teamwork, and clear, persuasive communication. These skills are essential for achieving effective interaction in various social and professional settings, enabling individuals to influence others constructively and strengthen interpersonal relationships (Goleman, 1995).

Regarding the first specific objective, it was found that the students exhibited difficulties in basic social skills. Courtesy and presentation skills, which involve good manners, respect, and politeness, require a positive emotional perception of others. Moreover, interpersonal communication skills—such as sharing personal information, asking questions, and listening attentively—are essential for the proper development of basic social abilities.

The results are consistent with those of Echevarría and Paredes (2025), who found that students experienced difficulties in developing social skills, particularly when initiating conversations. They also struggled to maintain attention and process information during interactions, as well as to interpret others' emotions, often showing insecurity when expressing their own opinions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

According to the general objective, it is concluded that the social skills of students in an educational institution in Lima-2024 revealed the presence of emotional difficulties, limitations in asking personal or general questions, and challenges in analyzing and reflecting before making decisions. Moreover, they tend to value positive emotions and consider clarification of misunderstandings important, while also requiring mental organization and personal planning for adequate coexistence. These factors contribute to difficulties in interacting appropriately with peers, hindering effective social relationships and potentially affecting their future interpersonal connections.

REFERENCES

- [1] Álvarez, M. (2020). Cognitive skills and didactic interaction strategy: a possibility through the questions asked in class. *Mendive*, 18(4), 857 – 867. <http://mendive.upr.edu.cu/index.php/MendiveUPR/article/view/2004>
- [2] Ansari, A. N. (2024). Student development of social capabilities and life skills: a mixed-methods study from Pakistan. *Cambridge Journal of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2024.2406426>
- [3] Arias, J., & Covinos, M. (2021). Diseño y metodología de la investigación. In *Enfoques Consulting Eirl* (Issue 1). https://gc.scalahed.com/recursos/files/r161r/w26022w/Arias_S2.pdf
- [4] Bandura, A., Ross, D., & Ross, S. A. (1961). Transmission of aggression through imitation of aggressive models. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 63(3), 575–582. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0045925>
- [5] Castillo Sangino, N. (2021). Phenomenology as a qualitative research method: questions from the research practice. *Revista Latinoamericana de Metodología de La Investigación Social*, 20(10), 7–18. http://www.relmis.com.ar/ojs/index.php/relmis/article/view/fenomenologia_como_metodo/167
- [6] CEPAL, C. E. para A. L. y el C. (2019). La Agenda 2030 y los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible Una oportunidad para América Latina y el Caribe. In *CEPAL*. <https://www.cepal.org/es/publicaciones/40155-la-agenda-2030-objetivos-desarrollo-sostenible-opportunidad-america-latina-caribe>
- [7] Cisterna, F. (2005). Categorización y triangulación como procesos de validación del conocimiento en investigación cualitativa. *Theoria*, 14(1), 61-71. <https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/299/29900107.pdf>
- [8] Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. (4th ed.). SAGE Publications. https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_609332/objava_105202/fajlovi/Creswell.pdf
- [9] Echeverría Caranqui, J. P., & Paredes Echeverría, C. A. . (2025). El desarrollo de habilidades sociales en estudiantes adolescentes desde una perspectiva educativa. *Revista InveCom / ISSN En Línea: 2739-0063*, 5(4), 1–8. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14962990>
- [10] Etikawati, A. I., Astuti, R. S., & Madyaningrum, M. E. (2023). A Qualitative Study to Explore the Construct of Communication Skills in Middle Childhood. *Journal of Educational, Health and Community Psychology*, 1(1), 107. <https://doi.org/10.12928/jehcp.v1i1.25684>

- [11] Goldstein, A. P., Sprafkin, R. P., Gershaw, N. J., & Kleiin, P. (1989). *Habilidades sociales y autocontrol en la adolescencia: Un programa de enseñanza*. Ediciones Martínez, Roca ISBN 842701287X. https://www.academia.edu/36322793/Habilidades_sociales_y_autocontrol_en_la_adolescencia_Goldstein_Sprafkin_Gershaw_y_Klein
- [12] Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. New York, NY: Bantam Books. ISBN 978-0-553-09503-6. http://www.cutonala.udg.mx/sites/default/files/adjuntos/inteligencia_emocional_daniel_goleman.pdf
- [13] Hernández Sampieri, R., & Mendoza Torres, C. P. (2018). Metodología de la investigación: las rutas cuantitativa, cualitativa y mixta. In *McGraw-Hill Education*. http://www.biblioteca.cij.gob.mx/Archivos/Materiales_de_consulta/Drogas_de_Abuso/Articulos/SampieriLasRutas.pdf
- [14] INEI. (2023). Intervenciones Del Ministerio De La Mujer Y Poblaciones Vulnerables-Mimp a Nivel Nacional Indicadores De Violencia-Inei. 1–11. <https://www.mimp.gob.pe/omep/pdf/resumen2/Boletin-Nacional-2024.pdf>
- [15] Irmansyah, J., Lumintuarso, R., Sugiyanto, F. X., & Sukoco, P. (2020). Children's social skills through traditional sport games in primary schools. *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 39(1), 39–53. <https://doi.org/10.21831/cp.v39i1.28210>
- [16] Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. New York, NY: Bantam Books. ISBN 978-0-553-09503-6. http://www.cutonala.udg.mx/sites/default/files/adjuntos/inteligencia_emocional_daniel_goleman.pdf
- [17] MIMP, & UNICEF. (2016a). *Entender para prevenir. Violencia hacia las niñas, niños y adolescentes en el Perú*. <https://www.unicef.org/peru/media/12441/file/informe-violencia-2016.pdf>
- [18] Nguyen, N.-P., Le, V.-T., Nguyen, H.-G., & Nguyen, T. T.-H. (2022). Teachers' awareness of happy schools with UNESCO items: a case study of a primary school in Hanoi, Vietnam. *Ministry of Science and Technology, Vietnam*, 64(2), 38–47. [https://doi.org/10.31276/vmostjossh.64\(2\).38-47](https://doi.org/10.31276/vmostjossh.64(2).38-47)
- [19] OECD/Eurostat. (2018). Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation. In *The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities*. <https://www.oecd.org/science/oslo-manual-2018-9789264304604-en.htm>
- [20] Paredes León, W. R., & Ramos Serpa, G. (2020). El aprendizaje cooperativo, educación desde la participación social en estudiantes de bachillerato. *Revista Científica UISRAEL*, 7(2), 75–92. <https://doi.org/10.35290/rcui.v7n2.2020.300>
- [21] Saavedra Melendez, J., Carrera Hidalgo, T. I., & López Caramantín, A. J. (2021). Inteligencia emocional y conductas agresivas en estudiantes de secundaria: un estudio de caso. *Sapienza: International Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 140–150. <https://doi.org/10.51798/sijis.v2i1.26>
- [22] UNICEF. (2020). Importancia del desarrollo de habilidades transferibles en América Latina y el Caribe. *Fondo de Las Naciones Unidas Para La Infancia (UNICEF)*, 65. https://www.unicef.org/lac/sites/unicef.org.lac/files/2020-07/Importancia-Desarrollo-Habilidades-Transferibles-ALC_0.pdf
- [23] Vestad, L., & Tharaldsen, K. B. (2022). Building Social and Emotional Competencies for Coping with Academic Stress among Students in Lower Secondary School. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 66(5), 907–921. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2021.1939145>
- [24] Zela Bravo, R. S. (2022). Inteligencia emocional y funcionamiento familiar en adolescentes estudiantes del nivel secundario. *Revista Científica de Ciencias de La Salud*, 15(1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.17162/rccs.v15i1.1754>